

ARTISANAL FOODS & BIOACTIVE BIOMOLECULES SEMINAR

19-21 December 2021, Arid Land Institute, Médenine, Tunisia

Artisanal Foods and Bioactive Molecules

19th - 22th December 2021 at Arid Land Institute, Médenine

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1. PREFACE

Changing consumer behavior and preferences for natural, healthy and tasty foods have contributed to the increasing interest in artisanal/traditional made products. “Artisanal food could be defined as food produced by non-industrialized methods, often handed down through generations. Tastes and processes, such as fermentation, are allowed to develop slowly and naturally, rather than curtailed for mass-production”. Fermented dairy and meat products are among the most consumed ones in the Mediterranean region. The safety of these products need to be improved and controlled whatever environment conditions and even in the absence of industrial facilities. AROMATIC 2018-2021 and ARTISANEFood-2019-2023 projects aim to develop simple, efficient and /or innovative bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, aiming to reduce and control of food-borne pathogens in artisanal fermented foods of meat or dairy origin.

Despite of COVID 19 pandemic lasting two years (2019-2021) and still not really controlled, pluridisciplinary researchers from different countries, confined in their laboratories continue to carry out their research activities and try to overcome difficulty and manage human fragility and limited material resources in order to achieve the objectives of their projects.

Certainly sharing passion for research, knowledge, skills and hardworking are the magic drug against all constraints, pushing us to continue our mission and encourage our young researchers to be perseverent and achieve their /our projects and maybe future professional challenges.

AROMATIC 2018-2021 and ARTISANEFood-2019-2023 projects are also sharing of a rich and diversified cultural heritage to valorise and to preserve. Maybe 2022-2023 will be the occasion for all partners to meet physically, communicate and disseminate main scientific research results and present their improved tasty artisanal products.

Many thanks to my colleague Halima ElHatmi and all my colleagues from IRA Mednine specially Prof. M. Hammadi and Prof. Khorchani for suggesting and helping to organize Artisanal Food and Bioactives Biomolecules Seminar at IRA Mednine and thanks to our partners and especially to Ursula Gonzales-Barron (Artisanefood Coordinator) and Alessandra De Cesare (Artisanefood Project Lead for Italian team) for their participation in this seminar.

Pr. Nourhene Boudhrioua,

Artisanefood Project Lead for Tunisian Team

2. PROJECTS PRESENTATION

ARTISANEFOOD PROJECT: to increase food safety in artisanal fermented milk and dried meat and sausage

PROJECT

Title: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

Acronym: ARTISANEFOOD

Budget: 1.583708 €

Period: 36 months (to be achieved May 2023)

Call: PRIMA-S2-2018-PIC2019

Number: PRIMA/0001/2018

AIMS

This main object of this project is to develop efficient bio-intervention strategies, enhanced process criteria, and an easy-to-use food safety decision support IT tool for participating artisanal food producers, aiming to the reduction and control of food-borne pathogens in 15 artisanal fermented foods of meat or dairy origin produced in Portugal, Spain, Italy, France, Greece, Morocco and Tunisia.

It consists of an integrated risk-based approach sustained by the concepts of:

- (i) extensive tracking surveys in the artisanal food chains, in order to identify origin, routes of contamination, risk factors favouring pathogens' survival, and technological causes for lack of homogeneity in the quality/safety of end-products;
- (ii) biopreservation, whereby functional starter cultures and natural extracts will be assessed as extra hurdles to ensure safety and extend shelf-life;
- (iii) fate studies of pathogens, predictive dynamic modelling,

and (iv) risk process modelling, for the delineation of the most effective biointerventions, optimisation of process variables and norms/standards, and design of quality monitoring tools.

CONSORTIUM

Nine pluridisciplinary scientific reseracher teams from 8 countries were involoved in artisanefood project as présenté in Table 1.

Table 1. Artisanefood consortium

PI name	Role, Organisation, Country
Ursula Gonzales-Barron ArtiSaneFood	Coordinator, Polytechnic Institute of Bragança, Portugal
Antonio Valero	Partner, University of Cordoba, Spain
Lihan Huang	Partner, USDA Agricultural Research Service, USA
Fanny Tenenhaus-Aziza	Partner, Centre National Interprofessionnel de l'Economie Laitière, France
Jean-Christophe Augustin	Partner, French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety, France
Spyridon Kintzios	Partner, Agricultural University of Athens, Greece
Gerardo Manfreda	Partner, University of Bologna, Italy
Achemchem Fouad	Partner, University Ibn Zohr, Morocco
Nourhene Boudhrioua Mihoubi	Partner, Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie Sidi Thabet, Manouba Université, Tunisia

MAINS WORK PACKAGES

Artisanefood project is performed through 8 work packages as follows:

Overall work plan and project target objective of ARTISANEFOOD project (Gonzales-Barron; 2019)

CONTRIBUTION OF TUNISIAN RESEARCH TEAM

Tunisian research team represented by researcher from ISBST (University of Manouba), IRA (University of Gabes) and INAT (University of Carthage) participates to the project through investigation of three traditional products: fermented milk 'Lben' and two fermented meat products: Merguez (sausage) and Kaddid (dried meat).

Consumers and local traditional producers from different regions of Tunisia participated to surveys performed to investigate consumers' attitude and perception of these artisanal products and natural ingredients and flowcharts used to produce these products.

Tracking surveys of the artisanal food productions were performed through physicochemical and microbial analysis of the working environment and on raw, mid and end products (WP). Innovative bio-preservation tools using natural vegetable extracts and / or lactic acid bacteria isolated from spontaneous fermented milk were characterized and tested for their antimicrobial activities against pathogenic strains (WP3-WP4). A series of fate studies of pathogens inoculated in prototype artisanal foods will be conducted (WP5) in order to understand the pathogens' viability during fermentation, ripening and storage under traditional manufacture process and enhanced manufacture variants (i.e., use of vegetables extracts, selected LAB strains and alternative process variables). The WP6, WP7 and WP8 are dedicated to (i) the dynamic modeling and safety optimization approaches, (ii) identification of the most suitable intervention strategies and (iii) establishment of an innovative safety decision-support IT tool.

<i>Traditional Products</i>	<i>Innovative biopreservatives approaches</i>
<p><i>Merguez: Dry sausage made with beef + spices</i></p>	
<p><i>Lben: Fermented cow milk</i></p>	
<p><i>Innovative safety decision-support IT tool</i></p>	

Natural bioactive molecules for safe and sustainable dairy products

Acronym: AROMATIC

PROJECT

ARIMNET 2 France-Tunisie-Egypte, 2018-2021

Principal investigators

PI NAME	PARTICIPANT ORGANIZATION NAME, COUNTRY	ROLE
Dr Emilie Dumas	BioDYMIA, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1 France	Coordinator
Dr. Halima El Hatmi	Institut des Régions Arides (Tunisie), Laboratoire d'Elevage et de la Faune Sauvage.	Partner
Dr. Samir A. Mahgoub	Zagazig University (Egypt), Department of Agricultural Microbiology	Partner

PROJECT SUMMARY

Dairy products play an essential role in providing essential nutrients such as proteins, vitamins and minerals. However, the poor sanitary quality of raw milk intended for direct consumption in certain Mediterranean countries, combined with unfavorable climatic conditions, leads to waste discharges when the overproduction of milk is associated with a lack of processing industries and / or poor refrigeration conditions. The AROMATIC project (ARIMNET 2 France-Tunisia-Egypt) aims to develop simple and effective methods using natural preservatives, drawing on traditional methods of cheese production and the potential of plants, to better protect raw milk against microbial contamination, before direct consumption or cheese making. The project is expected to provide simple methods that can be applied by small producers to improve the safety and quality of raw milk and its milk products, even in the absence of industrial dairy facilities.

CONSORTIUM AS A WHOLE

The proposal has a clear added value on being carried out on a transnational basis, since it involves 3 Mediterranean countries with different problematic concerning the use or the transformation of raw milk. However, these problematic can find common solutions. To be carried out, this project requires a multidisciplinary approach: microbiology, molecular biology, and biochemistry. This multidisciplinary can be found in the teams and persons involved in the project.

OVERALL WORK PLAN AND PROJECT TARGET OBJECTIVES

The overall work plan and participant involvement in planned activities is presented in the following scheme.

Overall work plan and project target objective of AROMATIC project (Dumas, 2018)

Bilateral TUNISO-PORTUGUESE project

Conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing: effects on product quality, safety, antioxidants and anti-diabetic potential

PROJECT SUMMARY

Strawberry is a non-climacteric fruit. It is harvested when berries are mature and attain the optimal ripeness in terms of color and eating quality. A strawberry is a rich fruit of phytonutrients, including polyphenolic antioxidants belonging to flavonoids, phenolic acids, lignans, tannins, and stilbenes. Strawberries are also excellent source of vitamin C, manganese; fiber, iodine, and folate; and a good source of copper, potassium, biotin, phosphorus, magnesium, vitamin B6, and omega-3 fats (alpha-linolenic acid). Strawberries are also recognized by the world healthiest food organization as the 5th best source of vitamin C at WHFoods. Strawberries polyphenolic compounds include essentially anthocyanins (responsible for the red colour in fresh strawberry), flavonoids, flavanols, ellagitannins (including small amounts of ellagic acid) and derivatives of hydroxycinnamic acid. Many authors reported that strawberries containing high levels of antioxidant and anti-inflammatory compounds could be associated with reduced risk of chronic diseases such as certain types of cancer and diabetes showed that strawberry antioxidants have favorable effects on postprandial inflammation and insulin sensitivity. They could potentially attenuate oxidative stress-related inflammatory changes resulting from the consumption of high-fat/carbohydrate meals. The authors showed that ellagitannins purified from strawberries had high α -amylase and low α -glucosidase inhibitory activities compared to whole fruit extracts of strawberries, indicating that whole strawberry fruits could be more beneficial for dietary management of early stages of hyperglycemia with higher α -glucosidase and fewer side effects from lower α -amylase. Despite of its high nutritional and healthy benefits, strawberries are highly perishable due to their high moisture content ($\geq 90\%$). Despite of numerous studies carried out on the effect of irradiation on microbial, sensorial and nutritional properties of strawberries, data reporting the effect of conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing on their antioxidants profiles, functional properties (e.g. anti-diabetic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and sensory profile are scarce. Besides, the role of reactive oxygen species (ROS) released due water radiolysis before and during storage is still unknown. This study will contribute to the body of knowledge on food technology and will be useful for scientists, professional and nutritionist to confirm if irradiated/processed strawberries preserve the same antioxidant potential and guarantee the safety and quality as those previously reported for fresh and freeze-dried ones.

AIMS

The aim of this project is to study the effect of conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing on product quality, safety, antioxidants profile and diabetic potential. *The specific objectives of the project are:*

- Determination of optimal irradiation conditions by E-beam and gamma irradiation based on safety and quality attributes,
- Determination of the effect of different treatments combination on the antioxidant profiles of strawberries,
- Selection of optimal treatment conditions to preserve strawberries bioactivity through the extraction of antioxidants and evaluation of cytotoxicity by using normal, cancer cell lines,
- Exploration of anti-diabetic effect of selected extracts.

TEAM

Dr. Sandra Isabel SILVA DAMAS CABO (Coordinator from Center For Nuclear Sciences And Technology)

Pr. Nourhene BOUDHRIQUA MIHOUBI (Coordinator ISBST, University of Manouba)

Salma Barkaoui, PhD, LR Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, ISBST, University of Manouba & Dr, Najla Miloud (Collaborator from National Center for Nuclear Sciences and Technologies CNSTN).

Project. National Program of Encouragement of Scientific Excellence, P2ES 2020-2022: Procédés intégrés et approches innovantes pour la valorisation et l'amélioration de la qualité des aliments traditionnels fonctionnels d'origine végétale (P2ES2020-D6P2)

PROJECT SUMMARY AND AIMS

The overall aim of this project is to improve the nutritional, functional and sensory properties of Bsisia and vegetable milk, two products among main traditional vegetables-based food through the development of new formulations that meet the specific needs of people with food intolerances (gluten or lactose intolerance, etc.), low calories diet or consumers wanting a vegetarian diet.

Plant-based beverages are innovative food presented as dairy milk alternative especially for consumers having preference to vegan diets and those having specific diet needs (lactose and cholesterol free, hypocaloric diet). The majority of these milk alternatives lack nutritional balance with a poor protein content but contain promoting health ingredients such as dietary fibers, minerals, antioxidants and vitamins. Vegetable beverages making involves the following steps: grinding blanched almonds into flour, addition of date's products and extraction with mineral water at ambient temperature, filtration and pasteurization. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the nutritional and the antioxidant properties of innovative drinks from dates and almonds as well as the co-products obtained from the extraction step. Bsisia is one of the most common traditional foods in Tunisia. It consists on a powdered preparation of roasted cereals (wheat and barley), leguminous seeds (fenugreek and carob), spices (fennel and anise) and some aromatic herbs (thyme and rosemary). Habitually, Bsisia is consumed as a beverage with water or milk, as well as, a paste mixed with olive oil. Customarily, sugar and honey were used as upfront sweeteners. Given the limited data available on Bsisia dietary value, the present work aimed to characterize the basic nutritional composition (fats, proteins, and carbohydrates), bioactive phenolic content, and to evaluate *in vitro* antioxidant capacities. The specific objectives of the project are:

1. The establishment on a laboratory scale of traditional methods of manufacturing foods of plant origin based on cereals, dried fruits or vegetables and fruits,
2. The determination of their nutritional and energy values as well as the desirable and undesirable components in terms of ingredients or properties,
3. The application of innovative approaches and optimized processes to improve the composition and properties of these products (all-natural additives, reduction in sugar and salt, optimization of the production process for vegetable milk, controlled fermentation of vegetable milk),
4. Evaluating the sensory and functional properties of end products and establishing awareness guidelines for consumers and professionals in the functional foods sector.

TEAM

Dr. Malek BenZid, Post-doctorant, Dr. Nesrine Rokbeni, Post-doctorant, Dr. Nahla Zeghonda: Engineer in transfer Technology, VACPA & Pr Nourhene Boudhrioua,

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Artisanal Foods and Bioactive Molecules

Tuniso-portuguese Project

3. SEMINAR PROGRAM

SCIENTIFIC SEMINAR

Artisanal Foods and Bioactive Molecules

The Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03 (ISBST, University of Manouba) and the Laboratory of Livestock and Wildlife, LR16IRA04 (Arid Land Institute of Medenine, IRESA, University of Gabes) organize a scientific seminar to present the main scientific research results obtained in the framework of the following multilateral, bilateral and national scientific research projects:

- ARTISANEFOOD PRIMA Project: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods. <http://www.ipb.pt/artisanefood/>
- ARIMNET AROMATIC Project : Natural Bioactive Molecules For Safe And Sustainable Dairy Products - Des molécules bioactives naturelles pour des produits laitiers sûrs et durables.
- TUNISO-PORTUGUESE Project: Conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing: effects on product quality, safety, antioxidants and anti-diabetic potential.
- National Program for Encouragement of Scientific Excellence, P2ES 2020: Procédés intégrés et approches innovantes pour la valorisation et l'amélioration de la qualité des aliments traditionnels fonctionnels d'origine végétale.

19th - 21th December 2021 at Arid Land Institute, Médenine

19th December 2021: Arrival at Médenine

20th - 21st December 2021: Scientific Research Program

22nd December 2021: Departure

Abstract submission to: artisanefood.prima@gmail.com before December 1st 2021

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P2ES project

Arrival Time	19/12/2021 Session	IRA Guesthouse Speaker
	20.12.2021 am	
8h45-9h10	Allocation of: Allocation of DG of IRA Medenine DG at the Higher Ministry of Education & Scientific Research	Mr Atallah G. Mme. Saida Rafrafi Farhat & Mme Hayet Souai
9h10-9h30	Allocation of LR Director of LR d'Elevage et Faune Sauvage de l'Institut des Régions Arides de Médenine	Prof. Hammadi M.
9h30-9h45	Presentation of ARIMNet-AROMATIC PROJECT	Prof. El Hatmi H.
9h45-10h00	Presentation of ARTISANEFOOD PROJECT Presentation of Tuniso Portuguese Project Presentation of P2ES Project	Prof. Boudhrioua N.
10h15-10h40	Coffee Break	
	20.12.2021 pm –Artisanefood	
	Moderators: Prof. Bellagha S. & Dr Essid I.	
10h40-11h00	Mini conference: Metagenomic application to artisanal food product characterization and risk assessment of foodborne pathogens. <i>A review</i> De Cesare, A., Mkadem W.	Prof. Alessandra De Cesare
11h00-11h15	Thermal Inactivation of <i>Listeria monocytogenes</i> in Chicken, lamb and beef meat using under vacuum cooking. Belguith K., Jalleb O., Periaq P.	Dr Belguith K.
11h15 -11h30	Isolation and characterization of LAB from spontaneous fermented cow and goat milks. Mkadem W., Khaoula B., Loussaif O., Elhatmi H., De Cesare A., Boudhrioua N.	Mkadem W.
11h30 -11h45	Antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal activities of extracts of traditional Tunisian spices. Ben Hmidène I., Belguith K., Ben Hsouna A., Brini F., Boudhrioua N.	Ben Hmidène, I. With Google meeting
11h45-12h00	Optimization of the Tunisian traditional kaddid recipe. Zioud A., Hajji W., Chabbouh M., Essid I., Bellagha S.	Zioud A. With Google meeting
12h00-12h15	Comparison of antioxidants, antibacterial and antifungal activities of phenolic extracts of two agrifood coproducts. Benabdallah M., Ghali R., Belguith K., M'hiri N., Ayachi Z., Ben Chaouacha-Chekir R., Boudhrioua N.	Ben Abdallah M. With Google meeting
12h15-12h30	Nutritional and antioxidant and antimicrobial properties of a halophyte plant <i>Salicornia Arabica</i> . Chrigui S., Jemai H., Ben Chaouacha-Chekir, R., Boudhrioua, N.	Chrigui S.
12h30-13h00	Discussion Q/R	All participants
13h00-1400	Lunch	
	Moderators: Prof. Bellagha, S. & Dr Belguith K.	
14h00-14h15	Consumer perception of ionizing radiation on strawberries Barkaoui S. Cabo verde S., Boudhrioua N.	Barkaoui S. With Google meeting
14h15-14h30	Effect of Ionizing Radiation on strawberries. Barkaoui S. Cabo Verde S., Boudhrioua N.	Barkaoui S. With Google meeting
14h30-14h45	Bio-conservation of Tunisian traditional meat products. Essid, I., Zioud, A., Tibaoui, S., Smeti, S., Bellagha S.	Essid I.

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14h45-15h00	Evaluation of the nutritional profile and antioxidant activity of a traditional food commonly consumed in Tunisia, Bsisia Rokbeni N., Ben Zid M., Boudhrioua N.	Dr Rokbeni N.
15h00-15h15	Assessment of the nutritional and antioxidant properties of innovative date-based drinks and their by-products, Ben Zid M., Rokbeni N., Boudhrioua N.	Dr Ben Zid M.
15h15-15h35	Mini conference: Integrate Processing of foods and derivatives for ecofriendly industry: Cases of study fishmeal and citrus juice processing. Nourhene Boudhrioua Mihoubi, Tarhouni Asma, M'hiri Nouha	Prof. Boudhrioua N.
15h35-16h00	Mini conference: Predictive modeling as a tool for ensuring microbiological safety of traditional fermented foods. Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez	Dr Gonzales U. With Google meeting
16h00-16h15	Evaluation of technological potential of lactic acid bacteria isolated from non-ready-to-eat Alheira sausages produced in northern Portugal. Faria A.S., Fernandes N., Cadavez V., Gonzales-Barron U.	Dr Faria A. S. With Google meeting
16h15-16h30	Natural bio-preservatives in Portuguese alheira sausage: The effect of sage extract on the survival of Staphylococcus. Coelho-Fernandes S., Rodrigues G., Caroch M., Barros L., Cadavez V., Gonzales-Barron U.	Coelho-Fernandes S. With Google meeting
16h30-16h45	Technological and antimicrobial properties of indigenous LAB from Portuguese artisanal goat cheeses. Silva B. N., Faria A. S., Cadavez V., Teixeira J. A., Gonzales-Barron U.	Silva B. N. With Google meeting
16h45-17h00	Investigation of anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidative potentials of Tunisian medicinal plants in primary human coronary artery endothelial cells. Darej A., Margetts G., Zaibi M. S., Ben Chaouacha-Chekir R., Benlarbi M.	Darej A. With Google meeting
17h00-17h15	Effects of humic acid alone or combined to organic acids on health status and meat quality of broiler chickens. Asma Akaichi, Abdallah Jeballi, and Nourhene Boudhrioua Mihoubi	Asma Akaichi,
17h15-17h45	Discussion Q/R	All participants
21.12.2021 am-Arimnet-AROMATIC		
Moderators: Prof. El-Hatmi & Prof. Fakhfakh		
8h30-9h15	Conference on antibacterial activities of bioactive molecules from different plant extracts. Mahgoub S.A., Dumas E., Dupas C., Adt I., El-Hatmi H.	Prof. Mahgoub S.A
9h15-9h30	Biological activities of some medicinal plants. Tlili H., Ben Arfa A., Neffati M., Najaa H.	Dr Najaa H.
9h30-9h45	Recovery of bioactive compounds from tomato processing by-products and potential application in dairy products. Azabou S., Abid Y., Attia, H.	Dr Azabou S.
9h45-10h00	Effects of <i>Salvia rosmarinus</i> dry extracts into raw milk, yogurt and cheese preservation. Jrad Z., Oussaief O., Dbara M., Metoyer B., Adt I., Dumas E., El-Hatmi H.	Dr Jrad Z.
10h00-10h15	Production of a soft cheese with ultra-filtered goat's milk. Chahbani A., Jarray R., Jrad Z., Oussaief O., Ammar E., Kchaou N., El-Hatmi H.	Dr Chahbani A.
10h15-10h45	Discussion Q/R	All participants

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10h45-11h15	Coffee Break	
	Moderators: Prof. Khorchani T. & Dr Najaa H.	
11h15-11h30	Effect of adding date powder on the physicochemical and antioxidant properties of pasteurized camel milk during storage. Oussaief O., Jrad Z., Dbara M., Jemaa S., Ben Abdlaah S., El-Hatmi H.	Dr Oussaief O.
11h30-11h45	Study of the antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of Tunisian cardoon. Khorchani T., Jrad Z., Metoyer B., Oussaief O., Fattouch S., El-Hatmi H.	Khorchani T. With Google meeting
11h45 -12h00	Effect of the enzymatic hydrolysis on biological activities of milk whey proteins. Ben Yaakoub M., Jrad Z., Oussaief O., Azabou S., El-Hatmi H.	Ben Yaakoub M.
12h00 -12h15	Bioactive potential and structural characterization of sulfated polysaccharides from Bullet tuna (<i>Auxis rochei</i>) by-products Mezhoudi M., Salem A., Abdelhedi O., Fakhfakh N., Nasri M., Debeaufort F., Jridi M., Zouari N.	Mezhoudi M.
12h15-12h30	Valorization of marine co-products by extracting gelatin for food interest. Salem A., Mezhoudi M., Abdelhedi O., Fakhfakh N., Nasri M., Debeaufort F., Jridi M., Zouari N.	Salem A.
12h30-13h00	Discussion Q/R	All participants
13h15-14h15	Lunch	
14h15-16h15	Visit to the IRA laboratories and museum	All participants

SCIENTIFIC SEMINAR:

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4. SCIENTIFIC & ORGANIZING COMMITTEES

Scientific committee	Organizing committee
Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua, ISBST, UMA	Mr Gouider Atallah, DG IRA
Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA	Prof. Mohamed Hammadi, IRA
Dr Gonzales Ursula, CIMO-IPB, Portugal	Prof. Touhami Khorchani, IRA
Dr Alessandra De Cesare, Université de Bologne	Prof. Halima El-Hatmi, ISBAM & IRA
Prof. Antonio Valero, Université Cordoba	Prof. Nourhene Boudhrioua, ISBST, UMA
Dr Khaoula Belguith, ISBST, UMA	Dr Zeineb Jrad, IRA
Dr Cabo Verde Sandra, Université Lisboa	Dr Olfa Loussaif, IRA
Prof. Khorchani Touhami, IRA	Dr M'hiri Nouha, ISBST, UMA
Prof. Rafika BenChaoucha Chekir, ISBST, UMA	Dr Malek Benzid, ISBST, UMA
Prof. Mahgoub Samir, FA, Zagazig University, Egypt	Dr Nesrine Rokbeni, ISBST, UMA
Prof. Sihem Bellagha, INAT, UCAR	Ms Wafa MkaDEM, ISBST, UMA
Prof. Isabelle Adt, BIODYMIA-France	Mr Mohamed Dbara, IRA
Prof. Nacim Zouari, ISBAM	Mme Afef Mahjoubi, IRA
Prof. Nahed Fakfakh, ISBAM	Mr Mabrouk Lanouar, IRA
Dr Iness Essid, INAT, UCAR	Mr Mourad Smida, IRA
Dr Hanen Najaa, IRA	Mr Soufiane Errich, IRA
Dr Yosr Haffani, ISBST, UMA	Mr Chokri Khorchani, IRA
Dr Maha BenLarbi, ISBST, UMA	Ms Raida Ben Siff, IRA

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Tuniso-portuguese Project

5. ABSTRACTS

METAGENOMIC APPLICATION TO ARTISANAL FOOD PRODUCT CHARACTERIZATION AND RISK ASSESSMENT OF FOODBORNE PATHOGENS

De Cesare, A¹., Mkadem, W²

¹*Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences, Alma Mater Stidiorum-University of Bologna, via Tolara di Sopra 50, 40064 Ozzano dell'Emilia (BO), Italy*

²*Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, Higher institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet, University of Manouba, BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia*

*E-mail of the corresponding author: alessandra.decesare@unibo.it

Abstract

Foodborne illnesses caused by pathogens are a large and growing public health problem all over the world. The study of the behavior of these foodborne pathogens and their interaction with the whole food microbial ecosystem along the food chain enable the implementation of preventive measures to improve public health and safety at industrial scale. Currently, genomic tools like shotgun metagenomics has a great potential to be used to characterize the microbial population associated to foods and to assess the microbiological safety and to track pathogens during foods processing. Capacity building based on harmonized quality controlled operational systems within meta-omics approaches will be essential for the investigation of cross-border outbreaks and for risk assessments of foodborne microorganisms. This literature review summarizes the advantages and barriers associated to the application of metagenomics to investigate pathogens in foods and food related environments within the microbial ecosystem to which they belong.

Key words: *microbial ecosystem-shotgun metagenomics-microbial risk assessment- food chain*

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisane food: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods

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Tuniso-portuguese Project

THERMAL INACTIVATION OF *LISTERIA MONOCYTOGENES* IN CHICKEN, LAMB AND BEEF MEAT USING UNDER VACUUM COOKING

Khaoula Belguith¹, Oumaima Jalleb¹, Paola Peria²

¹ *Laboratory of physiopathology, Food and biomolecules, LR17ES03, Higher Institute for Biotechnology Sidi thabet, University of Manouba, Tunisia.*

² *Faculty of agricultural Engineering, University of Cartagena, Spaine*

*E-mail of the corresponding author: khaoula.belguith@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

In comparison to traditional cooking consisting of boiling at atmospheric pressure, under vacuum cooking method at low temperatures has different benefits. In fact, where traditional cooking causes a significant loss of vitamins, minerals, and enzymes due to the high cooking temperature, under vacuum method of cooking saves all these nutrients. The low temperature not only keeps the nutrients but also improves the meat organoleptic quality. Despite, anaerobic conditions created under the vacuum conditions, disfavoring microorganism's multiplication, low temperature remain a risk to control especially in the case of pathogen foodborne presence. *Listeria monocytogenes*, a foodborne pathogen, has been implicated as a causative agent of listeriosis with a high mortality rate, and thus, continues to be a pathogen of concern for the regulatory agencies and food industry. A wide variety of meats are contaminated with *L. monocytogenes*, with a various range of contamination incidence. To ensure safety under vacuum cooking of chicken, lamb, and beef meat, this study proposes to experimentally follow the variation in temperature and the survival of this pathogen at the heart of the product using an immobilization technique. The thermal inactivation at 60°C of *Listeria monocytogenes* inoculated in chicken, lamb and beef meat using under vacuum cooking technique in water bath during 60 min was processed. A microbiological time temperature integrator was developed to estimate the efficiency of thermal processes applied to the meat core. The heat resistance of *Listeria monocytogenes* was characterized by a decimal reduction value at 60°C of 6.65 min in breast chicken, 6.77 min in lamb, and 7.21 min in beef meat.

Keywords: *under vacuum cooking, Listeria monocytogenes, Chicken meat, lamb meat, beef meat*

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by Erasmus+ mobility.

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*Artisanal Foods and
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Tuniso-portuguese Project

ISOLATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA FROM SPONTANEOUS FERMENTED COW AND GOAT MILKS

Mkadem, W^{1.}, Belguith, K^{1.}, Loussaif, O^{2.}, Elhatmi, H^{2.}, De Cesare, A^{3.}, Boudhrioua-Mihoubi, N¹

¹Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie de Sidi Thabet, University of Mannouba, BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia

²Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, Arid Lands Institute of Medenine, University of Gabes, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia

³Department of Veterinary Medical Sciences, Alma Mater Stiorum-University of Bologna, via Tolara di Sopra 50, 40064 Ozzano dell'Emilia (BO), Italy

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: mkademwafa@gmail.com; nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

Lactic acid bacteria are the most important groups amongst microbial diversity in the food chain. They contribute to enhance the shelf life of different food products through their fermentative activity or their ability to limit the development of other microorganisms. Research has confirmed how specific strains are involved in food with bio-preservatives properties by the production of organics acids, hydrogen peroxide, and bacteriocins. Therefore, this study aims to isolate and characterize potential bio-preservative lactic acid bacteria from goat and cow milks during spontaneous fermentation. A total of 156 presumed lactic acid bacteria (141 from fermented goat milk and 15 from fermented cow milk) were isolated. They were preliminarily characterized through morphological, physiological, lactose fermentation, and hemolytic assays. They were also characterized for technological properties based on milk acidifying capacity. 76 isolates were retained after preliminary screening. Spectrum antimicrobial efficacy of lactic bacteria isolates were evaluated against *Listeria monocytogens* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by spot on the lawn method and microplate (MP) assay of cell-free supernatants. Principal components analysis (PCA) was used to separate selected lactic acid bacteria isolates according to their *anti-Listeria* and *anti-Staphylococcus* potential. Two clusters were selected from PCA analysis among 76 isolates, lactic bacteria with higher antimicrobial potential (24 isolates) and those with lowest antimicrobial potential (23 isolates). Those isolates were subjected to co-aggregation and anti-biofilm tests against *Listeria monocytogens* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. One cluster included 8 isolates that demonstrated highest co-aggregation and anti-biofilm activities and 4 isolates with the lowest activities were identified by 16 S rRNA ribosomal gene sequence analysis. Isolates were identified as *E. faecium*, *E. faecalis*, *E. durans*, *L.paracasei*, and *L.fermentum*. Lactic acid bacteria isolates (*L.paracasei*, and *L.fermentum*) included in qualified presumption of safety list can be used as multi-functional bio-preservatives strains for dairy and food processing. However, the safety of identified *E. faecium*, *E. faecalis*, *E. durans* will be confirmed by the whole genome sequencing analysis.

Key words: *Lactic bacteria- anti-Listeria- anti-Staphylococcus – goat milk*

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods

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ANTIOXIDANT, ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITIES OF EXTRACTS OF TRADITIONAL TUNISIAN SPICES

Ben Hmidène, I. ^{a*}; Belguith K. ^a; Ben Hsouna, A. ^b; Brini, F. ^b; Boudhrioua, N. ^{a*}

^a *Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet, University of Manouba, BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunis*

^b *Biotechnology and Plant Improvement Laboratory, Centre of Biotechnology of Sfax (CBS), University of Sfax, B.P "1177" 3018 Sfax, Tunisia.*

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: ibtissem.benhmidene@inat.u-carthage.tn nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

Notable efforts achieved in recent years to enrich our knowledge of the bioactivities of herbs and spices, considered mostly as flavor enhancers or preservatives. Though, limited reports described the synergistic or antagonistic effects of their combinations. In the present work, antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal activities of the ethanolic extract of seven Tunisian culinary spices mixtures; coriander, carvi, paprika, fennel seed powder and mint were examined and compared in addition to their total polyphenolic and flavonoids contents.

The results of the present investigation showed that the extract of the mixture containing the same amounts of paprika, and fennel exhibited the lowest anti-free radical activity with $42.01 \pm 1.74\%$ and the highest content of total phenols and flavonoids, 1.04 ± 0.04 g GAE/100g DW and 1.022 ± 0.01 g Querc/100g DW. The lowest content of total phenols (0.74 ± 0.01 GAE/100g DW) was detected in the mixture containing 48.5 % of paprika and 12% fennel seed.

The antibacterial activity against 8 selected food spoilage and pathogenic bacteria. of the extracts were evaluated by three methods: the diffusion in wells on agar medium, the microplate micro-dilution method using the MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations) and MBC (Minimum Bactericidal Concentration). The extracts are active against most of the tested bacteria exhibiting inhibition diameters varying between 7 and 17.57 mm. Likewise, The MICs and MBCs of the extracts vary from 0.78 to 50 mg / ml for the eight strains tested.

The antifungal activity against 4 selected fungi were evaluated by the diffusion in wells on agar medium and the inhibition diameters of the extracts vary between 7 and 15 mm. All the extracts were active against *Aspergillus Niger*. The summarizing results showed that some of these extracts are promising natural antibacterial alternatives for food processing facilities against broad range of pathogens.

Key words: culinary spices, antioxidant, antibacterial, antifungal MIC, MBC

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods

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Tuniso-portuguese Project

OPTIMIZATION OF THE TUNISIAN TRADITIONAL KADDID RECIPE

Zioud A^a; Hajji W^a; Chabbouh M^a; Bellagha S^a; Essid I^a

PATIO UR17AGR01, Institut National Agronomique de Tunisie (INAT), Université de carthage, Tunisie

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: amirazioud@gmail.com

Abstract: For centuries, spices and herbs have been part of the traditional culinary culture of peoples. They have often been used for their medicinal, colouring and flavouring properties. Nowadays, several studies focus on the antioxidant capacities of these bio-ingredients in order to be used for the bio-preservation of food. For this reason, spices represent a powerful alternative for the food industry in response to consumer demand. Kaddid is a traditional Tunisian product prepared from salted, seasoned and dried meat. Seasoning is an important step towards obtaining the desired organoleptic characteristics.

The aims of this study are first to optimize the spice formula used for seasoning traditional kaddid by an experimental design and to evaluate the effect of the selected spices as food bio-preservatives on kaddid to prevent oxidation of the meat during storage.

To achieve these objectives, two spices were chosen for the experimental design: coriander and garlic powder. These spices are the most used in the preparation of traditional Tunisian kaddid according to the results of a recent survey. The level of incorporation was established on the basis of the results of preliminary trials conducted using different concentrations of each spice and on the basis of sensory attributes. Drying was carried out by sun-drying for 8 days then the product was stored for 45 days.

Optimal spices concentrations with respect to the antioxidant activity and sensory attributes of garlic powder and coriander were 4% (W/W) and 6% (W/W) respectively. The TBARS measurements carried out on kaddid to study the effect of spices on lipid oxidation during storage showed a significant effect on quality preservation.

Key words: Spices- Kaddid- formulation- experimental design

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisan food: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Food

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Tuniso-portuguese Project

COMPARISON OF ANTIOXIDANTS AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES OF PHENOLIC EXTRACTS OF TWO AGRI-FOOD COPRODUCTS

**Benabdallah, M.^{a*}; Ghali, R.^c; Belguith K; M'hiri N.; Ayachi, Z.^c; Ben Chaouacha-Chekir, R.^a,
Boudhrioua, N.^{a*}**

^aLaboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet, University of Manouba, BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunis

^bLaboratory of Toxicology CAMU, Tunis

^cAyachi, Group Herbes de Tunisie, Siliana, Tunis

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: benabdallah.mariem94@gmail.com; nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

Olive leaves of the Chemlali and Chetoui varieties and citrus peels of the Maltese orange variety were used for the preparation of extracts rich in oleuropein and hesperidin using a conventional solvent extraction method. The extraction yields for all the extractions protocols used for olive leaves are between 2.5% and 11% and for citrus peels the extraction yield is equal to 6%. The total phenol content for the leaves of the Chemlali and Chetoui variety and citrus peels varies between 0.01 and 6,6 g EAG / 100 g of powder. The antioxidant activity for the two co-products varies between 34% and 78%, respectively. The antibacterial activities of the extracts were determined by the diffusion method in wells on agar medium and eight reference bacterial strains ATCC were tested which are (*Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.) The extracts tested are active against some of these bacteria with inhibition zone varying between 8 and 19± 0,6 mm. The antibacterial activity of these extracts is confirmed by the microplate micro-dilution method by MIC (Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations), followed by determination of MBC (Minimum Bactericidal Concentration). The MICs and MBCs of the extracts vary from 6.25 to 100± 0,4 mg / ml for the eight strains tested. After testing the biological activities of the extracts, the two biomolecules Hesperidin and oleuropein were quantified by the HPLC method and as a preliminary analysis for the extraction protocol number 4 from olive leaves we found an oleuropein content equal to 1.3 mg / ml for the Chetoui variety and a content of oleuropein equal to 0.7 mg / ml for the Chemlali variety leaves and for citrus peels the hesperidin content equal to 0.31 mg / ml. The results obtained open a promising way to use these industrial food co-products for bio preservation applications in the food industry and for nutraceutical uses,

Key words: *Hesperidin, Oleuropein, Phenols, antioxidants, Minimum inhibitory Concentration, Minimum Bactericidal Concentration*

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NUTRITIONAL AND ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF AN HALOPHYTE PLANT *SALICORNIA ARABICA*

Chrighi S., Jemai H., Ben Chaouacha-Chekir, R.^a, Boudhrioua, N.^{a*}

^aLaboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, LR17ES03, Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet, University of Manouba, BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunis

^bLaboratory of Toxicology CAMU, Tunis

^cAyachi, Group Herbes de Tunisie, Siliana, Tunis

*E-mail of the corresponding author: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

The nutritional, antioxidants and antimicrobial characteristics of *Salicornia arabica* leaves, a food halophyte plant belonging to *Chenopodiaceae* were investigated. Fresh *Salicornia arabica* is a hypocaloric plant characterized by its high moisture and ash contents and low fat, protein and carbohydrates contents. Twenty fatty acids were identified in *Salicornia arabica* leaves. Fat content (~ 3 g/100 g dry basis) is composed by ~ 58% unsaturated fatty acids and 36% of saturated fatty acids. Palmitic acid, C16:0 was the dominant saturated fatty acid ($15.0 \pm 0.50\%$). Gadoleic acid, C20:1 ω 9 ($28.5 \pm 0.9\%$) and oleic acid, C18:1 (7.4 ± 0.5) were the most abundant mono-unsaturated fatty acids. *Salicornia arabica* leaves contain high content of polyunsaturated ω 9-fatty acids ($35.9 \pm 1.4\%$, g/100g db) compared to ω 3 ($4.7 \pm 0.4\%$) and ω 6-fatty acids ($14.5 \pm 0.9\%$). Glutamic acid, hydroxyproline, proline, aspartic acid, leucine, glycine, lysine, serine, arginine and alanine are the main amino acids of *Salicornia arabica* leaves which provide remarkably amounts of essential amino acids ~31% (1.98 g/100g dry basis). Decocted extract is rich in antioxidants and exerts a bactericidal action against eight reference bacterial strains ATCC. *Salicornia arabica* leaves are characterized by an interesting nutritional profile and antioxidants content having promising application as dietary supplement.

Keywords: *Salicornia arabica*, antioxidants activities, amino acids, antibacterial activities, fatty acids

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CONSUMER PERCEPTION OF IONIZING RADIATION ON STRAWBERRIES

Salma Barkaoui^{a,b,c} & Sandra Cabo Verde^b , & Nourhène M. Boudhrioua^{c*}

^a *Ecole Supérieure des Industries Alimentaires de Tunis, University of Carthage, Avenue Alain Savary 58, 1003 Tunis, Tunisia*

^b *Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares (C2TN), Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, E.N. 10 ao km 139.7, 2695-066 Bobadela LRS, Portugal*

^c *Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie de Sidi Thabet, Université de la Mannouba, LR17ES03 BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia*

*E-mail of the corresponding author: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

The aim of this work was to investigate the knowledge and the attitude of consumers towards irradiated products in general and irradiated strawberries in particular. The survey results revealed that 60.7% of Portuguese and 43.7% of Tunisians do not know what irradiation is, of which 53% of Portuguese believe that irradiation can have a health risk against 45.4% of Tunisians who are sure that the irradiation presents a health risk. 62.7% of Portuguese who responded will be tempted to buy irradiated strawberries against 16.6% who responded by refusing, unlike 33.5% of Tunisians who would refuse to buy irradiated strawberries. The answer to the question of the purchase intention of irradiated strawberries offered on the market, revealed that 46.7% of Portuguese will be tempted to buy against 62.7%. However, 33.5% of Tunisians answered the total refusal of the purchase intention, against 16.6% of Portuguese.

Key word: Strawberries. Food irradiation. Consumer intention. Mediterranean population

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by TUNISO-PORTUGUESE PROJECT: Conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing: effects on product quality, safety, antioxidants and anti-diabetic potential.

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EFFECT OF IONIZING RADIATION ON STRAWBERRIES QUALITY

Barkaoui.,S^{1,2,4}., Cabo Verde, S²., Najla B. Miloud³ & Boudhrioua., N^{4*}

¹*Ecole Supérieure des Industries Alimentaires de Tunis, University of Carthage, Avenue Alain Savary 58, 1003 Tunis, Tunisia*

²*Centro de Ciências e Tecnologias Nucleares (C2TN), Instituto Superior Técnico, Universidade de Lisboa, E.N. 10 ao km 139.7, 2695-066 Bobadela LRS, Portugal*

³*Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie de Sidi Thabet, Université de la Mannouba, LR17ES03 BP-66, 2020 Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia*

⁴*Centre National des Sciences et Technologies Nucléaires, 2020 Sidi Thabet, Tunisia*

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

The aim of this work at first was to study the effects of ionizing radiation (gamma and electron beam) in combination with storage (14 days) at 4 °C on the microbiological, physicochemical, sensory properties and bioactive content of fresh strawberries. In this sense, this work can provide a better understanding of the use of these eco-friendly technologies for food processing, considering the shelf-life extension with the potential added benefit of bioactivity improvement. The applied doses of ionizing radiation (gamma and e-beam) significantly decreased the proliferation of mesophilic aerobic bacteria, total coliforms, molds and yeast. The ionizing radiation treatment of fresh strawberries with gamma and e-beam at 2 kGy decreased the populations of aerobic bacteria at least 1 log CFU/g and fungi and yeasts to non-detectable levels up to 7 days of refrigerated storage. The effects of both gamma radiation and e-beam on firmness and weight loss of strawberries during refrigerated storage indicated to be dose-dependent, with an increase of weight loss and the decrease of firmness with the increase of radiation dose. However, a significant decrease of redness and chroma was noticed. Irradiation at 2 kGy can preserve the antioxidants of strawberries during refrigerated storage. The sensory analysis indicated the strawberries irradiated at 2 kGy (gamma and e-beam) as the most appreciated by the trained panelists.

Key words: Strawberries. Food irradiation. Bioactive content. Consumer intention. Mediterranean population

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by TUNISO-PORTUGUESE PROJECT: Conventional and non-conventional strawberries processing: effects on product quality, safety, antioxidants and anti-diabetic potential. Besides the main results of the first year of project 'Encouragement of Excellence Scientific

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BIO-CONSERVATION OF TUNISIAN TRADITIONAL MEAT PRODUCTS

Essid, I^{1*}., Zioud, A¹., Tibaoui, S²., Smeti, S²., Bellagha S¹.

1-National Agronomic Institute of Tunisia, Research unity UR-17AGR01, Carthage University

2-National Institute of Agronomic Research of Tunisia -Laboratory of Animal and Forage Productions, Carthage

**E-mail of the corresponding author: essisiness@gmail.com*

Abstract

Tunisian traditional meat products are less consumed these last years, due to life style change and high price. Despite their high protein content, vitamins and iron, meat products are susceptible to lipid oxidation that can deteriorate their sensory properties. In addition to lipid oxidation and autolytic enzymatic spoilage, microbial deterioration also plays a major role in quality deterioration of meat products. The use of antioxidants and antimicrobial additives is becoming necessary to extend shelf life of meat products. Dry sausages are one of the oldest known traditional meat products in Tunisia. In the past, they were often homemade for religious celebrations. Nowadays, most dry sausages are produced all year round both in butcher's shops and sausage manufacturing companies. The meat and fat are finely ground and seasoned with salt and other spices. Chemical additives are not used. The mixture is then stuffed into natural casings. Sausages are dried naturally at ambient temperature until reaching the desired dehydration. Our work aimed to extend shelf life of the dry sausages by natural additives: (i) selected starters and (ii) natural extracts of plant such as rosemary powder.

For the first work, results showed that the use of starter cultures could be useful for maintaining hygienic quality of sausages by inhibition of spoilage and pathogenic microorganisms, which allows a good preservation of sausages and consequently improved their shelf life. Textural parameters of sausages were not affected by the use of selective starters.

The results of the second work showed that rosemary powder added at 2 and 4 % improved microbiological quality by decreasing total viable and total coliform counts. Similarly, moisture and pH were affected by adding rosemary powder. Therefore, sausages added with 2 % of rosemary powder were the most appreciated by the panelists. This level of inclusion could be of interest for sausage preparation.

Key words: dry sausage, quality, starters, rosemary powder

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EVALUATION OF THE NUTRITIONAL PROFILE AND ANTIOXIDANT ACTIVITY OF A TRADITIONAL FOOD COMMONLY CONSUMED IN TUNISIA: “BSISSA”

Nesrine ROKBENI*, Malek BEN ZID, Nourhène BOUDHRIOUA*

Laboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules, Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie de Sidi Thabet, Université de La Mannouba, LR17ES03 BP-66, 2020, Ariana-Tunis, Tunisia

*E-mail of the corresponding author: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn, rokbeninesrine@gmail.com

Abstract

Bsissa is one of the most common traditional foods in Tunisia. It consists on a powdered preparation of roasted cereals (wheat and barley), leguminous seeds (fenugreek and carob), spices (fennel and anise) and some aromatic herbs (thyme and rosemary). Habitually, Bsissa is consumed as a beverage with water or milk, as well as, a paste mixed with olive oil. Customarily, sugar and honey were used as upfront sweeteners. Given the limited data available on Bsissa dietary value, the present work aimed to characterize the basic nutritional composition (fats, proteins, and carbohydrates), bioactive phenolic content, and to evaluate *in vitro* antioxidant capacities. The extraction procedure of phenolic compounds from powdered Bsissa was carried out in an ultrasonic bath using ethanol: water (80:20). In a sample of twenty-four brands of commercialized powder of Bsissa, with different formulas composition, the content on total proteins, carbohydrates, lipids and the minerals founded, respectively in the ranges of 9-21g, 66-82g, 1-6.9g and 2-3.5 per 100g of Bsissa. Consequently, the average calculated energetic value of the investigated samples ranges from 361 to 409 kcal/100g of Bsissa. Moreover, the total phenolic content varied significantly according to formulations within a range of 70 up to 451 mg Gallic acid equivalents/g of Bsissa. *In vitro* antioxidant assays using 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical scavenging and metal chelating activity (MCA) were quantified using BHT and EDTA, respectively. Interestingly, among all the tested samples, Bsissa containing barley/carob showed the most potent DPPH radical scavenging inhibition (91%; 520 mg Eq. BHT/ 100g of Bsissa). Conversely, the highest capacity for chelating metal ions was reported for wheat based sample (90%; 85 mg Eq. EDTA/100g of Bsissa). The results revealed that Bsissa have an important nutritional profile and interesting antioxidant properties, so it should be promoted as a potential functional food used for therapeutic purposes.

Key words: Traditional food, Bsissa, Nutritional value, Antioxidant activity, functional food

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by: P2ES project : Procédés intégrés et approches innovantes pour la valorisation et l'amélioration de la qualité des aliments traditionnels fonctionnels d'origine végétale

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ASSESSMENT OF THE NUTRITIONAL AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES OF INNOVATIVE DATE-BASED DRINKS AND THEIR BY-PRODUCTS

Malek Ben Zid, Nesrine Rokbeni and Nourhene Boudhrioua Mihoubi

Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet

Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules laboratory (Laboratoire de Physiopathologie, Alimentation et Biomolécules), LR17ES03

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn, malek_benzid@outlook.fr

Abstract

Plant-based beverages are innovative food presented as dairy milk alternative especially for consumers having preference to vegan diets and those having specific diet needs (lactose and cholesterol free, hypocaloric diet). The majority of these milk alternatives lack nutritional balance with a poor protein content but contain promoting health ingredients such as dietary fibers, minerals, antioxidants and vitamins. Vegetable beverages making involves the following steps: grinding blanched almonds into flour, addition of date's products and extraction with mineral water at ambient temperature, filtration and pasteurization. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the nutritional and the antioxidant properties of innovative drinks from dates and almonds as well as the co-products obtained from the extraction step. The procedure of beverages making involves the following stages: grinding blanched almonds into flour, addition of date's products and extraction with mineral water at ambient temperature, filtration and pasteurization at 90 °C for 1 min. Five drinks were produced. The formulation of the first beverage, served as a control, has been inspired by a traditional Tunisian recipe of almond drink known as rozata. It consists of blanched sweet almonds (10 % w/w), blanched bitter almonds (2 % w/w) and water. The date-based beverages include in addition to blanched almonds, dates at Tamr stage, dates at Bisser stage, date powder and date syrup (20 % w/w). The nutritional composition and the antioxidant properties of ingredients, beverages and co-products were examined. The sensory attributes of the beverages were assessed using descriptive analysis and acceptability tests. Results revealed that the almond based beverage was composed of 93% of water, 3.98 % of fats, 2.17 % of proteins and 0.76% of carbohydrates with low energetic value of 47.58 Kcal/100 g. It showed low total phenolic content TPC (3.05 mg GAE/100 g w.b) and low DPPH inhibition (23.07% -11.63 mg Trolox equivalent/100 g w.b). The addition of fresh and processed dates enhanced the nutritional and the antioxidant properties of beverages by increasing ash, carbohydrates and TPC of samples. Bisser based beverage exhibited the lowest levels of ash (0.30 %), carbohydrates (6.43 %), TPC (10.37 mg GAE/100 g w.b) and DPPH inhibition (48 %- 26.77 mg Trolox equivalent/100 g w.b). Date powder and date syrup beverages exhibited the highest levels of ash (0.58 %), carbohydrates (14 to 15 %), TPC (43.04 mg GAE/100 g w.b) and DPPH inhibition (84 %- 48.5 mg Trolox equivalent/100 g w.b). The residue of almond drink showed the highest content of ash (1.13 %), fats (24.17 %) and proteins (13.17%) and the lowest levels of carbohydrates (2.93 %), TPC (19.41 mg GAE/100 g w.b) and DPPH inhibition (49 % - 11.44 mg Trolox equivalent/100 g w.b). Residues from date powder and syrup beverages showed the highest levels of TPC (42 -45 mg GAE/100 g w.b) and DPPH inhibition (87-91 %). The results of sensory evaluation showed that the beverage made from date powder was the most appreciated.

Key words: fruit-based drinks, by-products characterization, nutritional properties, antioxidants, sensory evaluation

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by P2ES Project "Procédés intégrés et approches innovantes pour la valorisation et l'amélioration de la qualité des aliments traditionnels fonctionnels d'origine végétale".

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INTEGRATE PROCESSING OF FOODS AND DERIVATIVES FOR ECOFRIENDLY INDUSTRY: CASES OF STUDY FISHMEAL AND CITRUS JUICE PROCESSING

Nourhene Boudhrioua Mihoubi, Tarhouni Asma, M'hiri Nouha

Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Sidi Thabet

Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules laboratory, LR17ES03

**E-mail of the corresponding author: nourhene.boudhrioua@isbst.uma.tn,*

Abstract

Food processing generates co-products containing ingredients with promoting uses in connected industries. Application of integrate food processing allows more environment protection, generation of added-values and process sustainability. The aim of this work is to present through two cases of study (juice production and fishmeal production), the concept of integrate processing for consumers' welfare, environment respect and support of circular economy. The first example presented an integrated process for sardine valorization (flesh and co-products) based on blanching and or cooking, drying and then grinding to produce sardine flesh powder and sardine co-products fishmeal with sardine oil. The second example shows the potential industrial applications of coproducts recovered from citrus juice processing. The challenges related to recovered food co-products according to their added values and potential ingredients valorization will be analyzed. Antioxidants extraction from Maltese citrus peels by using conventional solvent extraction, microwave assisted extraction, ultrasound-assisted extraction, high-pressure extraction, and supercritical CO₂ extraction, will be discussed.

Keywords: orange peel, sardine, integrate process, coproducts, circularly economy

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PREDICTIVE MODELLING AS A TOOL FOR ENSURING MICROBIOLOGICAL SAFETY OF TRADITIONAL FERMENTED FOODS

Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1*} and Vasco Cadavez¹

¹*Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal; vcadavez @ipb.pt*

**Correspondence: ubarron@ipb.pt; Tel.: +351-273-303-325*

Abstract

The Mediterranean artisanal fermented foods constitute not only important engines for the regional economies, but they are part of the cultural heritage to preserve. The elaboration of these products results from the producers' knowledge and the invisible action of beneficial bacteria. However, spoilage and pathogenic bacteria are also lurking, and the producers must rely on a set of barriers that oppose their growth, namely: low contamination of raw materials, addition of salts (nitrites/nitrates) and condiments, low pH, low A_w , smoking, etc. Thus, for further valorisation of traditional foods, it is necessary to ensure their quality and safety. This is where predictive microbiological modelling should come into play, making it possible to predict survivability of bacteria considering the environmental conditions at which foods are subjected.

Predictive microbiological models that characterise the kinetics of pathogenic bacteria in fermented products should be of the dynamic type, and fed with laboratory data concerning the relevant microorganism challenged under the hurdles of salt, antimicrobials and microbial competition with lactic acid bacteria.

Today, we are witnessing the growth of computing power and the development of web applications for predictive microbiology that are globally available. Thus, it is time for artisanal food producers to benefit from these scientific and technological advances to inform their decisions on the safety of their products as well as their process design. This presentation will be focused on the theoretical concepts of the most appropriate predictive microbiology models for fermented foods, as well as on the presentation of some practical cases of dynamic models applied to these products.

Key words: *Pathogens; Lactic acid bacteria; Predictive microbiology; Dynamic modelling*

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA-funded project ArtiSaneFood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

SCIENTIFIC SEMINAR:

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EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGICAL POTENTIAL OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA ISOLATED FROM NON-READY-TO-EAT *ALHEIRA* SAUSAGES PRODUCED IN NORTHERN PORTUGAL

Ana Sofia Faria¹, Nathália Fernandes¹, Vasco Cadavez¹ and Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1,*}

¹Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal

* Correspondence: ubarron@ipb.pt; Tel.: +351-273-303-325

Abstract

Alheira is a non-ready-to-eat fermented sausage, traditionally from Northern Portugal, and produced without the aid of any starter culture. The aim of this study was to isolate lactic acid bacteria (LAB) naturally present in these sausages and test their technological potential for use as functional starters. Forty artisanal alheira sausages from 8 different producers were analysed, and 335 lactic acid bacteria strains were isolated from both MRS and M17 media. The antimicrobial potential of these strains was tested in vitro against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Salmonella* Typhimurium at 10°C and 37°C. A subset of the 63 most promising strains were screened for their acidifying and proteolytic activity, as well as lactic acid production. Two separate Principal Component Analyses (PCA) were used to assess the adequacy of the strains, for both MRS and M17-grown isolates. Results showed that acidification activity, followed by pathogen inhibition, were the most determinant characteristics for strain differentiation in both MRS and M17 isolates.

For MRS strains, PC1 explained 39% of data variability and correlated with high acidification capability of strains. PC2 (20%) characterised higher antimicrobial activity at lower temperatures, while PC3 (13%) allowed differentiation between strains with good proteolytic activity and lactic acid production. For M17 strains, PC1 (44% of data variability) characterised strains with higher acidification, while PC2 (20%) discriminated between strains with high *Salmonella* inhibition at 10°C and strains with high lactic acid production. PC3 (12%) was highly correlated only with *S. aureus* inhibition at 10°C. PCA maps for MRS strains identified three clusters: one with greater acidifying potential linked to better *S. aureus* inhibition at 37°C; a second cluster with greater pathogen inhibition and linked to higher proteolytic activity; and a third cluster of strains with quicker lactic acid synthesis. Regarding M17 strains, no clustering was detected.

The maps highlighted several strains with both high acidification potential and great pathogenic inhibition, desirable attributes when designing a tailored starter culture for application in *alheira* sausages.

Key words: Non-ready-to-eat; sausages; biopreservatives; principal component analysis

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NATURAL BIOPRESERVATIVES IN PORTUGUESE ALHEIRA SAUSAGE: THE EFFECT OF SAGE EXTRACT ON THE SURVIVAL OF *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*

Sara Coelho-Fernandes¹, Gisela Rodrigues¹, Caroch M. ¹, Lillian Barros¹, Vasco Cadavez¹ and Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1,*}

I. Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal; sara.coelho@ipb.pt, giselar0608@hotmail.com, mcarocho@ipb.pt, lillian@ipb.pt, vcadavez@ipb.pt

*Correspondence: ubarron@ipb.pt; Tel.: +351-273-303-325

Abstract

Essential oils and extracts of sage (*Salvia officinalis*) have shown strong inhibitory capacity against pathogens, such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, when tested in fermented foods. Alheira is a traditional non-ready-to-eat sausage produced mainly in Northern Portugal, which has in the past shown moderate prevalence of *S. aureus*. Thus, the aim of this study was to evaluate the antimicrobial effect of sage ethanolic extract against *S. aureus* in alheira sausages exerted during the stage of maturation.

Dry extract of sage aerial parts was obtained using ethanol 80% (v/v) and distilled water as solvents. Alheira batter was produced and added with 0.0%, 0.5%, 1.0% or 1.5% of sage (w/w), and stuffed in pre-washed natural casings to reach an individual weight of ~85 g. They were then inoculated with a *S. aureus* overnight culture to reach ~5 log CFU/g, and hung in a climatic-controlled chamber at 10 °C/85% RH for 10 days. Humidity, pH, water activity (*a_w*) and *S. aureus* counts were determined every two days.

While the alheira pH (pH₀=5.95) did not change significantly (p>0.05) during maturation, *a_w* in time followed an exponential decay model, dropping from 0.9913 to 0.9780. *S. aureus* population decreased according to a downward concave Weibull model in 1.00, 1.12 and 1.23 log CFU/g, when alheira was formulated with 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5% sage extract, respectively. By contrast, in the control treatment (0%), *S. aureus* counts did not change significantly (p>0.05) throughout maturation.

This work demonstrated that sage extract has a beneficial effect in controlling *S. aureus* in alheira during the maturation stage. This outcome is very relevant to regional producers since this frequently-found pathogen is mostly introduced to the batter through inadequate manipulation when mixing and stuffing.

Key words: *Salvia officinalis*; fermented sausage; *Staphylococcus aureus*; pH; *a_w*.

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA-funded project ArtiSaneFood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

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TECHNOLOGICAL AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF INDIGENOUS LAB FROM PORTUGUESE ARTISANAL GOAT CHEESES

Beatriz Nunes Silva^{1,2}, Ana Sofia Faria¹, Vasco Cadavez¹, José António Teixeira², Ursula Gonzales-Barron^{1*}

¹ Centro de Investigação de Montanha (CIMO), Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Campus de Santa Apolónia, 5300-253 Bragança, Portugal; ² CEB – Centre of Biological Engineering, University of Minho, Campus Gualtar, 4710-057 Braga, Portugal

*ubarron@ipb.pt

Abstract

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are involved in the cheesemaking fermentation process and can act as biopreservatives and promoters of desirable organoleptic characteristics. In this sense, the objective of this work was to select LAB strains for potential application in cheese manufacture. For this, isolation and characterisation of strains with antibacterial activity and suitable technological properties, such as proteolytic and acidifying capacities, were carried out from four batches of goat's raw milk cheeses (n=20). The antimicrobial activity was evaluated against *L. monocytogenes* (LM), *S. aureus* (SA) and *S. enterica* ser. Typhimurium (SALM) by the spot-on-lawn assay.

In total, 232 LAB strains (97 from MRS agar; 135 from M17 agar) were isolated. Antimicrobial tests at 37 °C revealed that 98%, 100% and 100% of MRS-isolated LAB presented antagonism against LM, SA and SALM, respectively. In contrast, only 13.3% and 28.1% of M17-isolated LAB exhibited antagonism against LM and SALM, respectively (no antagonism was observed against SA).

After selecting isolates with considerable antimicrobial activity at 37 °C (distance between halo circumference and LAB colony limit greater than 5 mm for SA, or 8 mm for LM and SALM – for MRS agar; or greater than 0.5 mm for SA, 6 mm for LM or 3.5 mm for SALM – for M17 agar), 84 strains (58 from MRS agar; 26 from M17 agar) were subjected to the spot-on-lawn assay at 10 °C for 10 days. The acidifying and proteolytic capacities were also screened *in vitro*.

From this subset, all LAB maintained their antimicrobial activity. Overall, M17-isolated LAB presented greater proteolytic and acidifying capacity (pH < 5.3 after 6 h) than LAB strains isolated from MRS agar.

These outcomes motivate the application of indigenous LAB selected in this study as a customised starter culture, to prevent pathogen growth and contribute to the development of attractive organoleptic properties in cheeses.

Key words: antibacterial activity; proteolytic activity; acidifying activity; biopreservation; starter culture

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by PRIMA project Artisanefood: Innovative Bio-interventions and Risk Modelling Approaches for Ensuring Microbial Safety and Quality of Mediterranean Artisanal Fermented Foods.

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INVESTIGATION OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANTI-OXIDATIVE POTENTIALS OF TUNISIAN MEDICINAL PLANTS IN PRIMARY HUMAN CORONARY ARTERY ENDOTHELIAL CELLS

Amina Darej^a, Gemma Margetts^b, Mohamed Sghaier Zaibi^b, Rafika Ben Chaouacha-Chekir^a, Maha Benlarbi^a

^aLaboratory of Physiopathology, Food and Biomolecules (PAB) of the High Institute of Biotechnology, Sidi Thabet (ISBST), University of La Manouba (UMA), BiotechPole Sidi Thabet, Sidi Thabet, Tunisia;

^bClore Laboratory, Faculty of Medicine and Biomedical Research, University of Buckingham, Buckingham, UK.

*E-mails of the corresponding author: maha.benlarbi@isbst.uma.tn

Abstract

Diabetes is frequently linked to oxidative stress, which can lead to a variety of metabolic problems, including cardiovascular disease (CVD). Many studies have shown that inflammation is also an important risk factor in the development of CVD. This study aimed to investigate the *in vitro* antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential effect of an olive leaf oleuropein (OLE)-rich extract in human coronary artery endothelial cells « HCAEC » that had been exposed to various hyperglycemic mimicking stages of diabetes and inflammatory conditions mimicking stages of obesity. The results showed that the HCAEC that were exposed to different glucose concentrations didn't produce reactive oxygen species (ROS) showing an absence of oxidative stress. On the other hand, the pre-treatment of the cells by OLE (20 μ M and 100 μ M) under hyperglycemic conditions during 24 or 48 hours induced an increase in the ROS level. However, our findings showed that OLE exhibited a protective effect by decreasing ROS in HCAEC caused by H₂O₂. Similarly, our data showed that OLE has a beneficial effect on Tumor Necrose Factor- α (TNF- α) and the Interleukine-1 β (IL-1 β) induced oxidative stress in HCAEC by decreasing ROS level. In addition, the OLE exhibited an anti-inflammatory effect by decreasing the expression of cellular adhesion molecule ICAM-1 in HCAEC induced by a differentiated adipocyte rich medium. Regarding the antioxidative and anti-inflammatory beneficial effects of OLE in HCEAC we conclude that oleuropein could be used for the prevention of CVD.

Key words: Oleuropein (OLE), Reactive oxygen species (ROS), Human coronary artery endothelial cells (HCAEC), Oxidative stress, Inflammation.

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ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES OF BIOACTIVE MOLECULES FROM DIFFERENT PLANT EXTRACTS

Samir A. Mahgoub^{*a}, Emilie Dumas^b, Coralie Dupas^b, Isabelle Adt^b, Halima El Hatmi^c

^a Agricultural Microbiology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagazig University 44511, Zagazig, Egypt

^b Univ Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, ISARA Lyon, BioDyMIA - Equipe Mixte d'Accueil n°3733, rue Henri de Boissieu, F-01000 Bourg en Bresse, France

^c University of Gabes, Arid Land Institute of Medenine, LR16IRA04 Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, 4100 Medenine, Tunisia, *E-mails of the corresponding authors: mahgoubsamir@gmail.com

Abstract

Contamination and cross-contamination of raw milk and dairy products with pathogenic bacteria can lead to public health epidemics. This problem is particularly important in the Mediterranean region where its consumption, mainly in the form of cheese and fermented milk, is significant. In addition, transport conditions are sometimes poorly suited to raw milk (hot climate, road infrastructure, etc.). In this context, the aim of this study was to supplement the dairy products (i.e., raw milk, artisanal cheese, etc.) by plant extracts (i.e., peptides from legumes, rosemary, thyme etc.) for the conservation and extension of dairy products. Plants are traditionally used to flavor, package or coagulate milk during the cheese making process. However, their potential as natural preservatives remain poorly studied. The current work targets Mediterranean plants used in cheese making as potential natural preservatives. For these reasons, legume protein hydrolysate, various ethanolic aqueous extracts of rosemary (*Salvia rosmarinus*) and thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*) from Tunisia and France have been studied. Results of antibiogram of *Listeria monocytogenes* Scott A and *Listeria innocua* strains were resistant to standard antibiotics like Ciprofloxacin (5 µg/disc), Gentamicin (10 µg/disc), Erthromycin (15 µg/disc), chloramphenicol (30 µg /disc) and Amoxicillin (30 µg /disc), and also Ampicillin (20 µg/disc) had very little effect against them. The resistant of all the Gram-negative bacteria to Aztreonam (10 µg/disc), and thus bacterial strains showed differential susceptibility to different antibiotics. The crude bioactive protein, crude bioactive peptides, rosemary, and thyme extracts showed significant antibacterial activity against these pathogenic bacteria. In this experiment crude, hot aqueous, cold aqueous and ethanolic extract showed inhibitory property towards all tested bacterial strains. Also, *L. monocytogenes*, *L. innocua*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Salmonella enterica*, *Escherichia coli* and *Pseudomonas aeregnosa* being most susceptible to the crude bioactive peptides and ethanolic extract (high concentrations) with inhibition zone ranged between 17.78 to 24.98 mm and 10.48 to 18.04 mm, respectively.

Key words: Antibacterial; Bioactive molecules; *Listeria*, *Salmonella*; Artisanal dairy products

Supporting Fund: This research was supported by ARIMNET AROMATIC Project: Natural Bioactive Molecules For Safe And Sustainable Dairy Products - Des molécules bioactives naturelles pour des produits laitiers sûrs et durables.

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BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF SOME MEDICINAL PLANTS

Tlili Hajar^{a*}, Ben Arfa Abdelkerim^a, Mohamed Neffati^a, Najjaa Hanen^a

^a Laboratory of Pastoral Ecosystems and Valorization of Spontaneous Plants and Microorganisms, Institute of Arid Regions (IRA), Medenine, Tunisia

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: hanen.najjaa@yahoo.fr

Abstract

This study explores the biochemical properties of six spontaneous plants, harvested in the arid Tunisian desert: *Marrubium vulgare* (L.), *Rhus tripartita* (Ucria) D.C., *Thymelaea hirsuta* (L.) Endl., *Plantago ovata* (Forsk.), *Herniaria fontanesii* (J. Gay.), *Ziziphus lotus* (L.). Various extracts have been prepared and studied for qualitative and quantitative chemical analysis, and HPLC / MS. Therefore, plant extracts have been used to determine different types of secondary metabolites (total polyphenols, flavonoids, tannins, carotenoids, saponins and alkaloids). Biological activities (anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antioxidant and anti-acetylcholinesterase) and the anti-proliferative effect on leukemia and colon cancer cell lines (K-562, THP-1 and CaCo-2 respectively) were studied. In order to better understand, the antiproliferative effect of *R. tripartita*, whole extracts and flavonoids compounds, on the proliferation of THP-1 via a negative regulation of the PI3K / mTOR pathway, different molecular analysis techniques (flow cytometry, qRT-PCR, and Western blot) was performed. The main results of this study have shown that the extracts obtained have an interesting anti-radical and antioxidant activity, compared to the DPPH radicals and metal ions (assay of the ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP)). Regarding their antibacterial activity, all plant extracts have shown an antimicrobial effect against *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and *S. epidermidis*, including strains resistant to methicillin. *Rhus tripartita* revealed the best MIC and MBC values and caused a significant decrease in the biofilm of *S. aureus*. *Rhus tripartita* has been shown to be particularly effective in the antiproliferative activity on leukemia cancer, in particular on the tumor cell line THP-1. All the species studied contain a remarkable quantity of different bioactive compounds, thus confirming their involvement in several biological activities and it would certainly have a wide scope in the future. In particular, the leaves of *R. tripartita* can be recommended therapeutically for the medicinal claims examined.

Key words: Flavonoids; Anticancerogenic activity; Biological activities; PI3K/AKT pathway

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RECOVERY OF BIOACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM TOMATO PROCESSING BY-PRODUCTS AND POTENTIAL APPLICATION IN DAIRY PRODUCTS

Samia AZABOU^{a*}, Yosra Abid^a, Hammadi Attia^a

^a *Laboratoire Analyse Valorisation et Sécurité des Aliments, ENIS, Sfax, Tunisia*

*E-mail of the corresponding author: azabousamia@yahoo.fr

Abstract

Tunisia is ranked between the top ten global manufacturers of processed tomato products with annual processing capacity of almost 650,000 to 950,000 t of fresh tomatoes which results in almost 20,000 to 30,000 t of solid waste material called « tomato pomace ». This by-product, consists mainly of peels and seeds, is unsuitable for direct human consumption and mostly disposed of as a solid waste. However, this by-product could serve as source of potentially valuable compounds to be processed inside the food chain as functional additives in different products. In fact, significant amounts of natural antioxidants like polyphenols and lycopene were simultaneously extracted from tomato peels using a food-grade solvent (ethanol). Afterwards, traditional Tunisian butter (TTB) which is one of the most appreciated dairy products in Tunisia, was enriched with antioxidants from tomato processing by-products (TPB) to evaluate their effect on its oxidative stability during 60 days of storage at 4 °C. TTB enriched with 400 mg of TPB extract/kg of TTB revealed the lowest peroxide values at all the determination intervals. Adding 400 mg of TPB extract/kg of TTB did not exhibit any undesired effect on lactic bacteria which are necessary for development of aroma and chemical properties of TTB. However, raw TTB and highly enriched TTB (800 mg of TPB extract/kg of TTB) displayed higher lipid peroxidation. The detrimental effect of high antioxidant amounts on TTB stability could be due to a possible pro-oxidant character. Thus, appropriate supplementation of TPB extract could be used in TTB as a protective agent against lipid peroxidation to extend its shelf-life up to two months.

Key words: Tomato by-products; Bioactive compounds; Traditional Tunisian butter; Oxidative stability

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EFFECTS OF *SALVIA ROSEMARINUS* DRY EXTRACTS INTO RAW MILK, YOGURT AND CHEESE PRESERVATION

Jrad Zeineb^{a*}, Oussaief Olfa^a, Dbara Mouhamed^a, Metoyer Benjamin^b, Adt Isabelle^b, Dumas Emélie^b, El-Hatmi Halima^{a,c}.

^a University of Gabes, Arid Land Institute of Medenine, LR16IRA04 Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, 4100 Medenine, Tunisia

^b University of Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, LAGEPP CNRS 5007, ISARA Lyon, BioDyMIA - Equipe Mixte d'Accueil n°3733, rue Henri de Boissieu, F-01000 Bourg en Bresse, France

^c University of Gabes, Food Department, Higher Institute of Applied Biology of Medenine, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia

*E-mail of the corresponding author: jradzeineb@yahoo.fr

Abstract

Contamination with foodborne bacteria is one of the most serious concerns in the food sector. Microbial contamination reduces the shelf life and quality of food, potentially resulting in life-threatening food illness. With this respect, a particular interest has been always accorded to rosemary (*Salvia rosmarinus*) extract as it generally exhibits important and confirmed antimicrobial activities. The aim of this study is the incorporation of rosemary extracts into milk to enhance its shelf life as well as yogurt and traditional cheese. Firstly, the hydro-ethanolic extracts (0%, 30% and 70%) of Tunisian rosemary were released by ultrasound at different temperatures, and their chemical analysis were then assessed. Secondly, their anti-oxidant and antibacterial activities were investigated. Finally, in order to evaluate the preservation effect of rosemary extracts, different rosemary 's hydro-ethanolic extracts at various levels were added to milk, yogurt and cheese. Obtained results indicated that the extract at 30:70% (water: ethanol) at 25 °C revealed an important free radical scavenging power ($IC_{50} = 15.6 \mu\text{g} / \text{ml}$), a strong inhibitory activity against the *Listeria innocua* and *Escherchia coli* and a content of polyphenols of 98.5 mg GAE / g. Thus, this extract was incorporated into raw milk contaminated with pathogen strains. The search for milk preservation suggested that hydro-ethanolic extract of rosemary presents the optimal efficiency against *E. coli*. The positive effects of hydro-ethanolic extract of rosemary have been proven, based on physicochemical, microbiological and sensorial qualities of cheese and yogurt. The results showed that rosemary extract extended significantly the shelf life of yogurt and artisanal cheese. Thereby, rosemary extract at 30:70% (water: ethanol) could be considered as a potential alternative of chemical food additives, particularly in milk and dairy preservation.

Key word: Rosemary extract; Raw milk; Artisanal cheese; Antibacterial activity; Preservation.

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PRODUCTION OF A SOFT CHEESE WITH ULTRA-FILTERED GOAT'S MILK

Amna Chahbani^{a*}, Rihab Jarray^b, Zeineb Jrad^c, Olfa Oussaif^c, Emna Ammar^b, Nabil Kchaou^b, Halima El Hatmi^{a,c}

^a*Département de l'Agro -alimentaire halle de Technologie Alimentaire (ISBAM)*

^b*Département Génie Biologique à l'Ecole Nationale d'Ingénieurs de Sfax (ENIS)*

^c*University of Gabes, Arid Land Institute of Medenine, LR16IRA04 Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, 4100 Medenine, Tunisia*

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: amnaw@hotmail.fr

Abstract

Goat's milk has better features than cow milk for human nutrition and health. This milk is rich in vitamins, minerals such as calcium, and mostly in medium chain fatty acids (Caproic, Caprylic and Capric acids) with about 15% of its total fatty acids content. That is why caprine milk shows better digestibility, and is recommended for malabsorption troubles. This study aims to increase nutritional contents such as proteins and minerals in goat's milk, using ultrafiltration process and to assess its effect on technological transformation in cheese production. The obtained ultrafiltrated goat's milk has significantly higher protein content, higher solid matter content and density as well as mineral content than raw goat milk. Moreover, the ultrafiltration process accelerated goat's milk coagulation without affecting the textural properties of the cheese compared to the commercialized one. As a result, the obtained soft cheese could be a promising new dairy product.

Key words: Ultrafiltration; Goat milk; Proteins; Soft cheese.

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EFFECT OF ADDING DATE POWDER ON THE PHYSICOCHEMICAL AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES OF PASTEURIZED CAMEL MILK DURING STORAGE

Oussaief Olfa^{a*}, Jrad Zeineb^a, Dbara Mohammed^a, Jemaa Sana^b, Ben Abdallah Samira^b, El Hatmi Halima^{a,b}.

^a *Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, Arid Lands Institute of Medenine, University of Gabes, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia*

^b *Agri-Food Department, Higher Institute of Applied Biology of Me'denine, University of Gabes, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia*

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: olfa.loussaief@hotmail.fr

Abstract

The objective of this work is to improve the sensory quality of pasteurized camel milk using date powder as a flavoring agent. Pasteurized camel milk was characterized in the absence and in the presence of date powder. The effect of cold storage (4 °C) on the physicochemical and antioxidant properties of pasteurized camel milk without and with date powder at different percentages (5, 10 and 15 %) was studied. The physicochemical analysis conducted were pH, acidity, viscosity, dry matter, ash and proteins. The antioxidant activity was evaluated using two in vitro tests: ABTS radical scavenging activity and ferric reducing antioxidant power.

The pH of pasteurized camel milk decreases after adding date powder. However, acidity, viscosity, dry matter, ash and protein content increases. In addition, the antioxidant activity increases after adding date powder to pasteurized camel milk. Microbiological analysis has shown that pasteurized milks (flavored or not) have good hygienic quality. Sensory analysis showed that date powder improved the overall acceptability of pasteurized camel milk. Pasteurized camel milk with the addition of 15% date powder is the most appreciated. When stored at 4 °C, the pH of pasteurized camel milk decreased while the acidity and viscosity increased. In addition, color, dry matter and ash remain stable. Pasteurized camel milk flavored with date powder retains its antioxidant power when stored at 4 °C. Date powder can be used as a flavoring agent to produce pasteurized camel milk with high nutritional value.

Key words: Camel milk; Pasteurization; Date powder; Antioxidant activity; Sensory analysis

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STUDY OF THE ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITIES OF TUNISIAN CARDOON

Takoua Khorchani^{a*}, Zeineb Jrad^b, Benjamin Metoyer^c, Sami Fattouch^a, Halima Hatmi^{a,d}

^a National Institute of Applied Sciences and Technology (INSAT),

^b University of Gabes, Arid Land Institute of Medenine, LR16IRA04 Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, 4100 Medenine, Tunisia

^c University of Lyon, Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, LAGEPP CNRS 5007, ISARA Lyon, BioDyMIA - Equipe Mixte d'Accueil n°3733, rue Henri de Boissieu, F-01000 Bourg en Bresse, France

^d University of Gabes, Food Department, Higher Institute of Applied Biology of Medenine, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: takouakhorchani@gmail.com

Abstract

The present work focused on several aspects aiming at the valorization of a plant widespread in Tunisia: *Cynara cardunculus L.* The qualitative study of some secondary metabolites revealed the richness of this plant in different phytochemical compounds of which one can quote the flavonoids and the phenolic acids, which have several therapeutic virtues and improve the preservation of food. As for the biological activities studied, the results showed a strong antioxidant power of *C. Cardunculus L.* Thus, a positive correlation can be established between the richness in phenolic compounds of extracts and their antioxidant capacities. However, this plant reveals a weak antibacterial power which was noticed only for *Listeria innocua*. This work shows that there is an important difference between the two studied parts of the plant: stems and leaves in terms of chemical composition and their potential activities. Thus, the 70% ethanolic extract of the leaves is the richest in flavonoids (4.78 mg Eq CA/g DM) and phenolic acids with a quantity of 40 mg Eq AG / g DM. It is 4 times greater than that found at the level of the rods for the same solvent. Moreover, the same leaves extract (70% ethanolic extract) gives the highest iron reducing activity (0.5 Eq mmol Fe²⁺ / g ES) and DPPH-radical scavenging activity (IC₅₀= 22.52 µg /ml).

Key words: *Cynara Cardunculus L.*; Chemical composition; Antioxidant activity; Antibacterial activity.

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EFFECT OF THE ENZYMATIC HYDROLYSIS ON BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITIES OF MILK WHEY PROTEINS

Ben Yagoub Meriem^{a,b*}, Jrad Zeineb¹, Oussaief Olfa^a, Azabou Samia^b, El-Hatmi Halima^{a,c}.

^a University of Gabes, Arid Land Institute of Medenine, LR16IRA04 Livestock and Wildlife Laboratory, 4100 Medenine, Tunisia

^b Analytical, Valorization and Food Safety Laboratory, National Engineering School of Sfax, Sfax, Tunisia

^c University of Gabes, Food Department, Higher Institute of Applied Biology of Medenine, 4119 Medenine, Tunisia

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: meriem.benyagoub@stud.enis.tn

Abstract

Throughout the present work, a comparative study was conducted to assess the physicochemical composition and the effect of digestive enzymes on biological activities of whey from milks of different animal species: camel, cow, goat, mare and ewe. In addition, whey proteins were successively hydrolyzed by pepsin and pancreatin using *in vitro* protocol simulating the gastrointestinal digestion. The profile of whey proteins and their degradation were characterized by electrophoresis. The SDS-PAGE analysis revealed the presence of homologous proteins between the five dairy species except that camel whey, which is characterized by the lack of β -lactoglobulin and the presence of two specific proteins (CWBP and PGRP). It also showed the different sensitivity of proteins after hydrolysis. Two whey proteins, α -lactalbumin and β -lactoglobulin, were more resistant to the digestive proteolytic enzymes than other proteins. Peptide concentration and hydrolysis degree were obtained by ortho-phthaldehyde method. After the gastrointestinal digestion, the highest levels of hydrolysis degree and peptide concentration were determined in the digested ewe whey sample (97.03 and 75.298%, respectively).

Undigested and digested proteins were tested for their antimicrobial, anti-obesity and antioxidant properties. Digested camel whey exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity against *E. coli*, whereas the highest anti-obesity activity was determined in the undigested camel whey proteins (87.32%). The highest antioxidant activity was found in ewe whey sample (51.46%) using the DPPH assay.

Key words: Milk; Whey proteins; Enzymatic hydrolysis; Biological activities; Bioactive peptides.

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BIOACTIVE POTENTIAL AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF SULFATED POLYSACCHARIDES FROM BULLET TUNA (*AUXIS ROCHEI*) BY-PRODUCTS

Maram Mezhoudi^{a,b*}, Ali Salem^a, Ola Abdelhedi^a, Nahed Fakhfakh^{a,b}, Moncef Nasri^a, Frederic Debeaufort^c, Mourad Jridi^{a,d}, Nacim Zouari^{a,b}

^a National Engineering School of Sfax (ENIS), University of Sfax, Laboratory of Enzyme Engineering and Microbiology, Sfax, Tunisia.

^b Higher Institute of Applied Biology of Medenine, University of Gabes, Medenine, Tunisia

^c Univ. Bourgogne Franche-Comté/AgrosupDijon, UMR PAM A02.102, Physical-Chemistry of Food and Wine lab., 1 esplanade Erasme, 21000 Dijon, France

^d Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Beja, University of Jendouba, Beja, Tunisia

*E-mail of the corresponding author: mezhoudi.maram@gmail.com

Abstract

Polysaccharides represented natural polymeric carbohydrate molecules that are widely distributed; they can be extracted from terrestrial and marine species. Marine organisms being very rich in carbohydrates, mostly in their sulfated and non-sulfated form, represented a good source of extractible polysaccharides. The present study deals with the isolation of sulfated polysaccharides (Ps) from the Bullet tuna by-products (head, skin and bones). To extract Ps from *Auxis rochei* waste (skin, bones head), cetylperidinium chloride (CPC) and ethanol were used as precipitating agent. Physicochemical, antioxidant, antibacterial and structural properties of the extracted polysaccharides were investigated. Then, the presence of sulfate groups in the extracted polysaccharides was further confirmed by FTIR analysis. Finally, sulfated Ps was used to control fish preservation during cooking by common analysis (pH change, color loss, lipid oxidation and spoilage). Results of chemical characterization revealed that Ps bones showed the highest total sugar, uronic acid and sulfate group contents. Tuna extracted-Ps contained a mixture of neutral sugars, with high amounts of glucuronic and galacturonic acids and presented different molecular weights. The chromatographic spectra revealed marked differences in Ps distribution, which depended on the extraction method. Interestingly, Ps-bones showed the highest antioxidant activity among all extracted Ps. Moreover, results revealed that all polysaccharides displayed varying degrees of antibacterial activity. Ps-bones exhibited high and wide spectrum of activities, inhibiting the growth of all tested bacteria. Ps-bones incorporated during fillet cooking offered an excellent protection of fish fillet by avoiding pH change, color loss, lipid oxidation and spoilage. Overall, the obtained results showed that Ps could be potentially used as natural antioxidant and antibacterial agents. Ps-bones, exhibiting the best antioxidant and antibacterial activities, and as a results, they can be used as promising natural substrate in different food systems.

Key words: Bullet tuna Sulfated polysaccharides; Monosaccharide composition; Infrared spectroscopic analysis; Antioxidant and antibacterial activities; Fish fillet preservation.

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VALORIZATION OF MARINE CO-PRODUCTS BY EXTRACTING GELATIN FOR FOOD INTEREST

Ali Salem^{a,b}, Maram Mezhoudi^{a,b}, Ola Abdelhedi^a, Nahed Fakhfakh^{a,b}, Moncef Nasri^a, Frederic Debeaufort^{c,d}, Mourad Jridi^{a,e}, Nacim Zouari^{a,b}

^a Laboratory of Enzyme Engineering and Microbiology, Engineering National School of Sfax (ENIS), University of Sfax, Sfax, Tunisia

^b High Institute of Applied Biology of Medenine, University of Gabes, Medenine, Tunisia

^cUMR PAM A02.102, Physical-Chemistry of Food and Wine Lab, University Bourgogne France Comté/AgroSupDijon, 1 esplanade Erasme, 21000 Dijon, France.

^d BioEngineering Department, IUT Dijon-Auxerre, 7 blvd Docteur Petitjean, 21078 Dijon Cedex, France.

^e Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Beja, University of Jendouba, Beja, Tunisia

*E-mails of the corresponding authors: alis22337@gmail.com

Abstract

This work aimed to valorize marine by-products by extracting high-value biopolymers. For this purpose, the extraction of gelatin from the smooth hound skin was performed, as well as the effect of the skin pretreatments (drying either by the oven or microwave) and the methods of gelatin drying (freeze-drying or spray drying). The highest yield was obtained with the freeze-dried gelatin from the non-treated fish skin. The results of the physico-chemical composition indicated that gelatins were mainly rich in glycine, proline and hydroxyproline. A slight increase in the protein content was observed in the freeze-dried gelatin obtained from the non-treated fish skin. The techno-functional and structural properties were also affected by the skins' pretreatments. Moreover, agar was added in the gelatin film-forming solution of the freeze-dried smooth hound gelatin in order to improve the mechanical properties and the UV and water barrier properties of the resulting films. On the other hand, *Lepidium sativum*, an edible Mediterranean plant, has been used for the extraction of phenolic compounds, known with interesting antioxidant and antibacterial activities. Furthermore, the coating effect of smooth hound gelatin gel enriched with the ethanolic extract of *L. sativum* seeds on the quality of chilled stored fish fillets was evaluated. The obtained results showed that gelatin coating reduced the changes in pH, total volatile basic nitrogen and weight loss, minimized bacterial proliferation and improved textural properties of fish fillets during storage at 4°C.

Keywords: Smooth hound Gelatin; Drying methods; Gelatin-agar films; Coating; *Lepidium sativum*.

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Fig. 1. Timeline of the evolution of the concept "traditional food" in the last twenty years

From 'What is a traditional food? Conceptual evolution from four dimensions. REVIEW ARTICLE. By Zeltzin Rocillo-Aquino et al. 2021. [Journal of Ethnic Foods.](https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-021-00113-4) [https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-021-00113-4.](https://doi.org/10.1186/s42779-021-00113-4)

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6. Communication

<http://ipb.pt/artisanefood/>

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<http://www.ira.agrinet.tn/index.php/8-actualites/316-l-institut-des-r%C3%A9gions-arides-organise-un-s%C3%A9minaire-scientifique-artisanal-foods-and-bioactive-molecules-20-21-d%C3%A9cembre-2021>

L'Institut des Régions Arides (Laboratoire Elevage et Faune sauvage, LEFS, LR16IRA04), l'Institut Supérieur de Biotechnologie-Sidi Thabet (LR Physiopathologie, Alimentation et Biomolécules, PAB, LR17ES03) et l'Institut Supérieur de Biologie Appliquée, Medenine en collaboration avec leurs partenaires, organisent un séminaire international "Artisanal Foods and Bioactive Molecules" 20-21 Décembre 2021.

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